

3-Dimethylsulphamido-10-[3-(4-methanesulphonyl-piperazino)propyl]phenothiazine Methanesulphonate as New Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(v) : Analysis of Vanadium Steels and Minerals

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3-Dimethylsulphamido-10-[3-(4-methanesulphonylpiperazino)propyl]phenothiazine methanesulphonate forms orange-red species with V^{V} in phosphoric acid medium. The species exhibits maximum absorption at 513 nm with a molar absorptivity of $9.26 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 0.1–6.3 ppm with an optimum concentration range 0.5–5.8 ppm. The method has been used successfully for the determination of vanadium in alloys and minerals.

MOST of the reagents proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(v) are extractive photometric reagents. The limitations of many of these reagents are narrow ranges of determination, lengthy procedures and interference by common ions. 3-Dimethylsulphamido-10-[3-(4-methanesulphonylpiperazino)propyl]phenothiazine methanesulphonate (DMPPM) is a tranquillising agent. In the present paper the authors have investigated the colour reaction between vanadium(v) and DMPPM, and developed DMPPM as a sensitive and selective reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(v). The proposed method offers the advantages of simplicity, selectivity, sensitivity, wider range of determination and reasonable stability without the need for extraction or heating.

Experimental

A Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements.

A stock solution of vanadium(v) was prepared from sodium metavanadate, standardised volumetrically with standardised iron(II) solution and diluted to give a standard solution containing $75 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of vanadium(v). A 0.1% (w/v) solution of DMPPM was prepared in double-distilled water and stored in amber bottle. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade reagents.

Procedure: An aliquot of the stock solution (containing 12.5–145.0 μg of V^{V}), 10 M phosphoric acid (15 ml) and 0.1% DMPPM solution (2 ml) were transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume made upto the mark with double-distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 513 nm against the reagent

blank. The amount of V^{V} was deduced from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

DMPPM reacts with vanadium(v) instantaneously to form orange-red species at room temperature ($27 \pm 1^\circ$) in hydrochloric, sulphuric or phosphoric acid medium. The coloured species is believed to be a radical cation¹. The study of the coloured species in hydrochloric or sulphuric acid medium is not recommended because the reaction is less sensitive, the colour is less stable and many foreign ions interfere even at low concentrations. Hence phosphoric acid medium is selected for the present study.

The maximum colour development is observed instantaneously in 3–8 M phosphoric acid medium. The stability of the colour increases from 6 min in 3 M phosphoric acid to 1 h in 8 M phosphoric acid. Below 3 M phosphoric acid the maximum intensity of colour is not obtained. Above 8 M phosphoric acid the absorbance slightly increases. A 6 M phosphoric acid medium in which the absorbance readings are stable for 50 min is selected for the present study.

The orange-red species exhibits maximum absorbance at 508–518 nm where vanadium(v) and the reagent do not absorb appreciably. The effect of reagent concentration was examined by measuring the absorbance at 513 nm of solutions containing 3 ppm of vanadium(v) and varying amounts of reagents. A 2-fold molar excess of the reagent over vanadium(v) is required to obtain maximum absorbance. The effect of varying temperature on the stability of the species was investigated. The absorbance values are not affected over the temperature

range 5–60°. Above 60°, the absorbance gradually decreases with increasing temperature.

Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 0.1–6.3 ppm of vanadium(v). The optimum range for the effective spectrophotometric determination evaluated by Ringbom's method is 0.5–5.8 ppm. The sensitivity of the reaction is 5.58 ng cm^{-2} and the molar absorptivity is $9.26 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 513 nm. The standard deviation calculated from five determinations in a solution containing 3 ppm of vanadium(v) is 0.004 and the relative error is less than 2%.

Effect of foreign ions: In order to assess the possible analytical applications of this reaction, the effects of some ions which often accompany vanadium have been studied by adding the ions in different amounts to $3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of vanadium in solution. An error of 2% in the absorbance reading is considered tolerable. The following amounts (ppm) of foreign ions were found to give less than 2% error in the determination of 3 ppm of vanadium(v): Fe^{III} , 1400; Fe^{II} , 3000 in presence of 1200 ppm fluoride; Al^{III} , 2000; Ni^{II} 3500; Mo^{VI} , 3375; Cr^{III} , 200; Cu^{II} , 700; Mn^{II} , 2400; Zn^{II} , 1500; Mg^{II} , 4200; Th^{IV} , 1325; U^{VI} , 1200; Ti^{IV} , 1200; flouride, 1600; chloride, 5800; bromide, 1200; iodide, 0.4; EDTA, 160; tartrate, 160; citrate, 7200; acetate, 12000; oxalate, 11000; nitrate, 9800; sulphate, 10400.

Analysis of vanadium steels: The sample (~0.5 g) of vanadium steel was accurately weighed and treated with 10 N sulphuric acid (15 ml), syrupy phosphoric acid (2 ml) and concentrated nitric acid (1 ml). When the initial brisk reaction subsided, the solution was carefully boiled to expell the oxides of nitrogen. The solution was cooled and diluted to 50 ml with double-distilled water. A 0.01 N potassium permanganate solution was added dropwise until the solution appeared pale pink. The solution was heated to about 50° and 0.01 N oxalic acid solution was added drop wise with stirring until the pale pink colour disappeared. The solution was cooled and made upto 100 ml with double-distilled water. A suitable aliquot of the solution was taken and the vanadium content determined using the standard procedure. The results are given in Table 1.

Analysis of ilmenite: The ilmenite sample (~0.5 g) was accurately weighed and fused with sodium hydrogen sulphate (~10 g) in a silica crucible until the sample completely decomposed. The melt was cooled and dissolved in hot 2 M sulphuric acid (50 ml). The solution was filtered and the filtrate diluted to 250 ml with double-distilled water. An aliquot (25 ml) of the solution was treated with 0.01 N potassium permanganate solution dropwise until the solution appeared pink in order to oxidise any V^{IV} to V^{V} . The solution was warmed and treated with 0.01 N oxalic acid solution with slow stirring until the pink colour of the solution disappeared. The solution was transferred

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN VANADIUM STEEL

Sample no.	Composition %	Vanadium	
		Certified value $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Found* $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
10820	C, 0.17; Si, 0.13;	1.40	1.40
	Mn, 0.53; Ni, 0.20;	2.80	2.75
	Cr, 0.20; Mo, 0.63;	3.73	3.75
	V, 0.28; Cu, 0.10;	4.67	4.60
	P, 0.015; S, 0.025		
T032	C, 0.56; Si, 0.24;	0.98	0.96
	Mn, 0.91; Ni, 0.23;	1.46	1.45
	Cr, 1.03; Mo, 0.04;	1.96	1.96
	P, 0.022; S, 0.018;	2.48	2.50
	V, 0.12; Cu, 0.19		
7110	C, 0.18; Si, 0.34;	2.02	2.00
	Mn, 0.33; Ni, 0.12;	3.02	3.04
	Cr, 1.08; Mo, 0.85;	4.03	3.99
	V, 0.87; Cu, 0.22;	5.04	5.05
	P, 0.018; S, 0.012;		
	Ti, 0.11; Al, 0.042		

* Average of five determinations.

to and diluted to a 100 ml mark with double-distilled water. Aliquots of the solution were used for the determination of vanadium as described in the standard procedure. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN ILMENITE

Sample	Composition %	Vanadium	
		Certified value $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Found* $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
MK Grade	TiO_2 , 54.2; Fe_2O_3 , 14.2;	0.64	0.64
	FeO , 26.6; Al_2O_3 , 11.25;	1.28	1.29
	MnO , 0.4; Cr_2O_3 , 0.07;	2.56	2.53
	MgO , 1.03; P_2O_5 , 0.12;		
	ZrO_2 , 0.8; SiO_2 , 0.68;		
	rare earths, 0.12; loss on ignition, 0.34; V_2O_5 , 0.16		

* Average of five determinations.

The results in Tables 1 and 2 show that other metals present in vanadium steels and the associated substances in ilmenite do not interfere in the determination of vanadium. The values obtained with the new reagent compare favourably with the certified values of vanadium.

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Reference

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